

Optical properties of chiral Schiff base Mn^{II}, Co^{II}, Ni^{II} complexes having azobenzene[†]

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As a promising renewable energy, dye sensitized solar cell (DSSC) has been developed to improve performance of every material and system. From the viewpoint of dye metal complexes/organic compounds, we have reported on chiral Schiff base (salen-type) metal complexes and induced CD from chiral Schiff base metal complexes involving azo-dye groups to Au nanoparticles, and recently we have also conducted research on their optical interactions. In this paper, we showed the results of Z-scan NLO measurements for the analogous achiral organic ligands and metal complexes.

Keywords: Schiff base, azobenzene, chirality, DFT, nonlinear optics (NLO).

Introduction

Dye-sensitized solar cell (DSSC), which can be prepared more easily and less expensively than silicon solar cell, has been expected to be next-generation energy in recent years¹⁻⁴. Generally, ruthenium (Ru) based metal complex dyes are used as DSSC dyes, and some results show its power generation efficiency is as high as around 10%. On the other hand, from a resource viewpoint that Ru is rare and expensive, alternative dyes using different metals have been studied⁵⁻⁸.

It is widely known that azobenzene has a large π -conjugation and undergoes *trans-cis* isomerization when being exposed to light of a particular wavelength. In addition, azobenzene behaves as liquid-crystal mesogens and its molecules can be anisotropically oriented by irradiating polarized light⁹⁻¹¹. Using the following advantages, we have conducted a study on chiral salen-type complexes as potential DSSC dyes¹²⁻¹⁴.

- (1) High stability as complexes due to chelate effect.
- (2) Structural diversity by introducing substituents.

- (3) Catalysis in asymmetric synthesis and oxidation reduction reaction.

Salen-type complexes, however, exhibit low absorbance in the UV-Vis spectrum, and its absorption wavelength range lies in the UV region¹⁵. In this research, azobenzene was introduced into salen-type complexes (Fig. 1) in order to increase absorbance and to extend the absorption range to the visible light region. We also expected that light irradiation

Fig. 1. Chemical structures of complexes (M^{II} = Mn^{II}, Co^{II}, Ni^{II} and for ACMn, ACCo and ACNi, respectively).

[†]Invited Lecture.

tion to the complexes can change and control its absorption range. We also studied the non-linear optical properties of the complexes to seek a possibility of imparting other functions.

Experimental

General procedures:

Chemicals of the highest commercial grade available (solvents from Kanto Chemical, organic compounds from Tokyo Chemical Industry and metal sources from Wako) were used as received without further purification.

Preparation:

To a methanol solution (15 mL) of 4,4'-((1*S*,2*S*)-1,2-diaminoethane-1,2-diyl)dibenzonate (0.150 g, 0.5 mmol)¹⁶, methanol solution (15 mL) of potassium hydroxide (0.096 g, 1.0 mmol) and 2-hydroxy-5-(phenyldiazenyl)benzaldehyde (0.226 g, 1.0 mmol)¹⁷ was added dropwise, and the resultant mixture was stirred at 313 K for 3 h. Then manganese(II) acetate tetrahydrate (0.125 g, 0.5 mmol) was added, and the solution was stirred for 3 h (while bubbling with N₂). After the reaction and filtration, the filtrate was concentrated under reduced pressure, to obtain a brown solid. This crude solid was washed with methanol and *n*-hexane to give rise to the ACMn complex. Synthesis of other metal complexes were carried out in the similar way instead of the corresponding metal sources (cobalt(II) acetate tetrahydrate or nickel(II) acetate tetrahydrate).

ACMn: Yield: 0.2710 g (67.7%). Anal. Found: C, 60.26; H, 3.02; N, 9.74%. Calcd. for C₄₂H₂₈K₂MnN₆O₆: C, 59.64; H, 3.34; N, 9.94%; IR (KBr, cm⁻¹): 540 (w), 689 (w), 768 (w), 833 (w), 1016 (w), 1070 (w), 1114 (m), 1154 (w), 1184 (w), 1222 (w), 1301 (m), 1395 (m), 1472 (w), 1540 (m), 1608 (s, C=N), 1624 (s, C=O), 2357 (w), 3411 (br, s, -OH). $\mu_{\text{eff}} = 5.39$ B.M. at 300 K (theoretical value high spin d⁵ 5.92 B.M.).

ACCo: Yield: 0.3000 g (74.3%). Anal. Found: C, 59.45; H, 3.44; N, 9.44%. Calcd. for C₄₂H₂₈CoK₂N₆O₆: C, 59.36; H, 3.32; N, 9.89%; IR (KBr, cm⁻¹): 539 (w), 630 (w), 689 (w), 713 (w), 768 (w), 785 (w), 834 (w), 1016 (w), 1117 (m), 1160 (w), 1186 (w), 1226 (w), 1261 (w), 1334 (w), 1385 (s), 1472 (m), 1540 (m), 1607 (s, C=N), 1668 (w), 1696 (w, C=O), 3407 (br, s, -OH). $\mu_{\text{eff}} = 2.60$ B.M. at 300 K (theoretical value high spin d⁷ 3.87 B.M.).

ACNi: Yield: 0.2606 g (64.8%). Anal. Found: C, 56.87; H, 3.96; N, 8.61%. Calcd. for C₄₂H₃₂K₂N₆NiO₈: C, 56.96; H,

3.64; N, 9.49%; IR (KBr, cm⁻¹): 554 (w), 689 (w), 768 (w), 833 (w), 1016 (w), 1116 (m), 1160 (m), 1184 (w), 1226 (w), 1253 (w), 1335 (w), 1386 (m), 1417 (m), 1471 (m), 1539 (w), 1608 (s, C=N), 1698 (w, C=O), 2336 (w), 2360 (w), 2927 (w), 3055 (w), 3433 (br, s, -OH). $\mu_{\text{eff}} = 2.52$ B.M. at 300 K (theoretical value high spin d⁸ 2.83 B.M.).

Physical measurements:

Elemental analyses (C, H and N) were performed using a Perkin-Elmer 2400 II CHNS/O analyzer at the Tokyo University of Science. Infrared (IR) spectra were recorded as KBr pellets on a JASCO FT-IR 4200 plus spectrophotometer in the range 4000–400 cm⁻¹ at 298 K. Electronic (UV-Vis) spectra were obtained on a JASCO V-570 UV-Vis-NIR spectrophotometer in the range 1500–200 nm at 298 K. Circular dichroism (CD) spectra were obtained on a JASCO J-820 spectropolarimeter in the range 900–250 nm at 298 K. Electrochemical (cyclic voltammetry, CV) measurement were carried out on a BAS SEC2000-UV/Vis and ALS2323 system with Ag/AgCl electrodes range of -0.50 – 0.80 V vs Ag/Ag⁺. The magnetic properties were investigated using a Quantum Design MPMS-XL superconducting quantum interference device (SQUID) magnetometer at an applied field of 0.5 T in the temperature range of 5–300 K.

Computational method:

Calculations of all complexes were performed using the Gaussian 09W software Revision D.02 (Gaussian, Inc.)¹⁸. All the geometries have been optimized by using B3LYP level of theory and SDD as basis set. Also, we performed frequency calculation on optimized geometry by using same level of theory and basis set also.

Results and discussion

UV-Vis spectra:

The UV-Vis spectra (Fig. 2) appeared intense π - π^* peaks at 377, 394, 400 nm for ACMn, ACCo, ACNi, respectively, which are shifted to longer wavelength region than the corresponding previous complexes without azo-moiety (e.g. 322 nm for Fe^{II} one). Due to π orbitals in the ligands, the bonds covered around 400 nm in particular ACMn exhibit a shoulder around 450–600 nm, for which DFT exhibited HOMO(A) \rightarrow LUMO+3(A) (61%) and HOMO-2(B) \rightarrow LUMO(B) (25%) transitions at 457.135 nm, HOMO-1(A) \rightarrow LUMO(A) (19%) and HOMO(B) \rightarrow LUMO + 3(B) (64%) transitions at 558.563

Fig. 2. UV-Vis spectra (in DMSO) for ACMn, ACCo, ACNi and previous Fe^{II} complex (Fe-L')¹⁵.

nm, respectively. Therefore, owing to introduction of azo moiety, three present complexes became to be useful dyes for DSSC in view of light absorption.

DFT calculation:

In every case this frequency calculation produced no imaginary frequencies, indicating that we had located minimum on potential energy surface. The optimized geometries are given below (Fig. 3).

We have performed UV-Vis spectra by using the optimized geometries in B3LYP/SDD level of theory in gas phase and we have plotted the major and transitions in each complex with oscillator strength (Fig. S4). Among all complexes the Co complex shows maximum absorbance.

Theoretically generated optimized structures of the complexes and their ground state energy show the stability order as [ACMn] (−2502.4841 a.u.) < [ACCo] (−2543.9481 a.u.) < [ACNi] (−2569.0534 a.u.). This apparently follows the electronic configuration (d⁵, Mn^{II}, five unpaired electrons, d⁷, Co^{II}, three unpaired electrons; d⁸, Ni^{II}, no unpaired electron with square planar, diamagnetic complex) and compatible with charge radius ratio (Radius: Mn^{II}, 97 pm; Co^{II}, 89 pm; Ni^{II}, 83 pm). Because of diamagnetic nature of [ACNi] no unpaired electron exists while Mn^{II} and Co^{II} complexes show both α- and β-phases of the MOs. These MOs are used to explain the electronic properties of the complexes. We have also carried out the density of states (DOS) and partial density of states (PDOS) by using same level of theory and basis set also to observe the bonding pattern in these complexes, along with the contribution of the core and the ligands towards the

Fig. 3. Molecular structures of complexes (ACMn, ACCo, ACNi).

frontier molecular orbitals (FMOs). Figs. 4 and 5 depict the selected occupied and unoccupied frontier orbitals of α- and β-functions of [ACMn] and [ACCo]. These two functional forms fluctuate significantly in some cases from energy and the composition. In [ACMn] the composition of HOMO shows that α-function carries 62% Ligand²⁻ and 38% Mn^{II} characteristics while β-function bears 98% L²⁻ and 2% Mn^{II} behavior. But in case of LUMO: α-function and β-function is composed of 100% L²⁻. Other MOs follow similar pattern of distribution except HOMO-1 (α-function: 96% L²⁻ and 4% Mn^{II} feature; β-function: 98% L²⁻ and 2% Mn^{II} character). The energy of MOs of α- and β-form of HOMO, is −127.757 kcal/

Fig. 4. PDOS with orbital contribution (ACMn).

Fig. 5. PDOS with orbital contribution (ACCo).

mol and -134.385 kcal/mol LUMO, is -57.267 kcal/mol and -57.217 kcal/mol respectively (Fig. S3). The HOMO and LUMO bring higher contribution of L^2 in both α - and β -function. Other unoccupied MOs (LUMO+1, LUMO+2 etc.) carry $> 95\%$ ligand characteristics.

The calculated transitions are grouped in Table 1. The intensity of these transitions has been assessed from oscillator strength (f). Herein, for ACMn the visible transitions (350–400 nm) are assigned to HOMO(α) \rightarrow LUMO+3 (37%) and HOMO-2(β) \rightarrow LUMO(β) is 14%. Intense band at 387 nm (f , 0.916) may be described as $d_{\pi}(\text{Mn}^{\text{II}}) \rightarrow p_{\pi}(\text{L})$. In

case of [ACCo] the composition of HOMO shows that α -function carries 98% L^2 - characteristics while β -function allows 94% L^2 - and 6% Co^{II} activities. Both α -function and β -function of LUMO carry $> 95\%$ ligand characteristics. All other occupied and unoccupied MOs are mainly bear ligand features. The energy of MOs of α - and β -form of HOMO is; -132.029 kcal/mol and -133.642 kcal/mo LUMO, -57.406 kcal/mol and -57.336 kcal/mol (Fig. S3). In case of [ACNi] the HOMO is 90% ligand character and 10% Ni character while all other MOs bear 98–100% ligand characteristics (Fig. 6).

Table 1. Summary of computational results

	Wavelength (nm)	Osc. strength	Symmetry	Major contribution	Minor contribution
Ni complex (ACNi)	423.241	0.8372	Singlet-A	HOMO>L+2 (57%), HOMO->L+4 (39%)	
	366.481	0.7337	Singlet-A	H-1->L+3 (60%), H-1->L+5 (38%)	
Co Complex (ACCo)	396.191	0.744	4.360-A	HOMO(A)->L+2(A) (31%), H-1(B)->L+1(B) (13%), H-1(B)->L+4(B) (19%), HOMO(B)->L+5(B) (14%)	HOMO(A)->L+4(A) (4%), H-1(B)->L+2(B) (2%), H-1(B)->L+7(B) (3%)
Mn Complex (ACMn)	387.024	0.916	6.225-A	H-2(A)->L+3(A) (37%), H-1(B)->L+2(B) (14%)	H-11(A)->L+5(A) (2%), H-10(A)->L+4(A) (2%), H-2(A)->L+2(A) (2%), H-2(A)->L+5(A) (7%), H-1(A)->L+4(A) (2%), H-9(B)->L+5(B) (2%), H-8(B)->L+1(B) (4%), H-2(B)->LUMO(B) (2%), H-1(B)->L+5(B) (2%), HOMO(B)->L+1(B) (2%), HOMO(B)->L+2(B) (6%), HOMO(B)->L+4(B) (2%), HOMO(B)->L+5(B) (2%)

Ni-L Complex

Fig. 6. PDOS with orbital contribution (ACNi).

In each case we have observed that the more contribution towards the FMOs are coming from the ligands.

Electrochemical properties:

Cyclic voltammetry is used to examine the redox nature of the complexes in DMSO in the potential range +1.00 to -1.50 V vs SCE as reference electrode.

Fig. 7 and Table 2 list HOMO-LUMO gap (E_g) and other electrochemical data obtained from CV measurement. For

Fig. 7. Electrochemical data.

Table 2. Electrochemical data

	Fe-L ¹⁵	ACMn	ACCo	ACNi
E_{ox} (NHE) (V)	1.069	0.813	0.802	0.786
E_{red} (NHE) (V)	-1.248	-1.088	-0.823	-1.078
HOMO (eV)	-5.509	-5.253	-5.242	-5.226
LUMO (eV)	-3.192	-3.352	-3.617	-3.362
E_g (eV)	2.317	1.901	1.625	1.864

all complexes, LUMO exists in a higher level than the TiO₂ conduction band (-0.50 V), and HOMO exists in a lower level than the iodine (I⁻/I₃⁻) HOMO (+0.40 V). Therefore, it is conceivable that all complexes can inject electrons into TiO₂ and restore function as a dye for DSSC. Comparing with the previous Fe^{II} complex¹⁵, these differences are ascribed to central metal predominantly.

The electrochemical observations are also supported by DFT computation. The HOMO of α -function of [ACMn] bears 38% Mn character hence oxidation is referred to Mn^{II}→Mn^{III}. Thus Mn^{III}/Mn^{II} redox couple is defined at 0.42 V. Since [ACCo] carries only 2% Co character and [ACNi] carries only 10% Ni character, thus it defines difficult oxidation and it is observed indeed.

Nonlinear optics:

Third-order nonlinear optical parameters were investigated using Z-scan technique^{21,22}. It is a simple and sensitive method, which provides not only the magnitudes of the real and imaginary parts of the nonlinear susceptibility, but also the sign of the real part. The third-order nonlinear optical parameters such as nonlinear absorption coefficient, nonlinear refractive index and third-order susceptibility have been investigated using both open and closed aperture Z-scan technique. The compounds ACMn, ACCo and ACNi were dissolved in DMSO solvent at 0.5 mM concentration. Z-scan measurement was performed using 532 nm Nd:YAG laser having 5 ns pulses at a repetition rate of 10 Hz with an incident intensity of 7.01 GW/cm². The laser beam was focused by a lens of focal length 10 cm and the radius of the beam waist was calculated as 35 μ m. The Rayleigh length Z_0 is estimated as 7.42 mm, is greater than the thickness of the sample cuvette (1 mm), an essential requirement for Z-scan experiments.

Third-order NLO parameter nonlinear absorption coefficient (β) were measured using open aperture Z-scan tech-

Fig. 8. Open aperture Z-scan curves of ACMn, ACCo and ACNi.

nique. Fig. 8 shows the open aperture (OA) Z-scan traces of ACMn, ACCo and ACNi in DMSO solvent. Here the normalized transmittance (T) is plotted against the sample position (Z). The obtained OA curves show reverse saturable absorption (RSA) property thus the absorption coefficient β is positive. For fitting the experimental data, the following equation is used

$$T(z, S=1) = \sum_{m=0}^{\infty} \frac{[-q_0(z,0)]^m}{(m+1)^{3/2}} \text{ for } |q_0| < 1 \quad (1)$$

where $q_0(z,0) = \beta I_0(z) L_{\text{eff}}$ and $L_{\text{eff}} = (1 - e^{-\alpha l})/\alpha$ is the effective thickness with the linear absorption coefficient α , I_0 is the irradiance at the focus. Where, ϵ_0 is the permittivity of free space, c is the velocity of light in vacuum. The experimental curve is well fitted with theoretical curve. The obtained values of β are presented in Table 3.

The closed aperture (CA) Z-scan technique was performed to determine the sign and magnitude of nonlinear refractive index (n_2). The closed aperture Z-scan plots of ACMn, ACCo and ACNi in DMSO solvent at 0.5 mM concentrations are shown in Fig. 9. The valley followed by a peak in the normalized transmittance indicated that sign of the refractive nonlinearity is positive due to self-focusing. The compounds ACCo and ACNi show positive nonlinear refraction while the Z-scan curve of ACMn shows peak to valley configuration indicates negative nonlinear refraction.

For the calculation of nonlinear refractive index, n_2 the

following equations are used

$$T(z, \Delta\phi_0) = 1 - \frac{4\Delta\phi_0 x}{(x^2 + 9)(x^2 + 1)} \quad (2)$$

where $\Delta\phi_0 = 2\pi (n_2 I_0(t) L_{\text{eff}}/\lambda)$ is the on axis nonlinear phase shift and $x = z/z_0$. The nonlinear refractive index n_2 was calculated by the eq. (3)

$$n_2 = \frac{\Delta\phi_0 \lambda}{2\pi I_0 L_{\text{eff}}} \quad (3)$$

From the values of n_2 and β , the real and imaginary part of the third-order susceptibility $\chi^{(3)}$ of the sample can be calculated

$$\text{Re } \chi^{(3)} (\text{esu}) = 10^{-4} \frac{\varepsilon_0 n_0^2 c^2}{\pi} n^2 \left(\frac{\text{cm}^2}{W} \right) \quad (4)$$

$$\text{Im } \chi^{(3)} (\text{esu}) = 10^{-2} \frac{\varepsilon_0 n_0^2 c^2 \lambda}{4\pi^2} \beta \left(\frac{\text{cm}}{W} \right) \quad (5)$$

The third order nonlinear susceptibility $\chi^{(3)}$ was computed using the relation

$$\chi^{(3)} = \left[(\text{Re } \chi^{(3)})^2 + (\text{Im } \chi^{(3)})^2 \right]^{1/2}$$

The calculated values of nonlinear absorption coefficient (β , m/W), the nonlinear refraction coefficient (n_2 , m²/W) and third-order nonlinear susceptibility ($\chi^{(3)}$, esu) are summarized in Table 3.

In comparison with other organic compound, the obtained values of $\chi^{(3)}$ are in the order of the nonlinearity optical susceptibility values of the organic NLO materials like fullerene and coumarin derivatives^{23,24} and it is lower than values of azo dye 1-(2,5-dimethoxy-phenylazo)-naphthalen-2-ol²⁵.

One of the important application of RSA behavior in material is its optical limiting property. Optical limiters are devices which are transparent at low input fluence and become opaque at high inputs. Optical limiters are devices that are used for the protection of human eyes and sensitive devices from laser induced damage. The optical limiting curves of the sample are extracted from the open aperture Z-scan data and are shown in Fig. 10. Here the normalized transmittance (T) is plotted against the input laser fluence. An important term connected to the optical limiting is optical limiting thresh-

Fig. 9. Closed aperture Z-scan curve of ACNi, ACCo and ACMn.

old (O_{LT}). The lower the optical limiting threshold is better for the optical limiting material. The optical limiting threshold of

Table 3. Third-order nonlinear optical parameters of ACCo, ACNi, and ACMn

Sample Concentration (mM)	Solvent	$\beta \times 10^{-11}$ (m/W)	$n_2 \times 10^{-19}$ (m ² /W)	$\text{Re}\chi^{(3)} \times 10^{-13}$ (esu)	$\text{Im}\chi^{(3)} \times 10^{-13}$ (esu)	$\chi^{(3)} \times 10^{-13}$ (esu)	OL Threshold (J/cm ²)
0.5	ACNi	0.9184	4.7262	3.1665	2.5294	4.0527	21.30
0.5	ACCo	1.0828	5.5472	3.6089	2.9822	4.6183	16.32
0.5	ACMn	1.3718	-3.4205	-2.2860	3.7781	4.4158	11.06

Fig. 10. Optical limiting response of ACMn, ACCo and ACNi.

ACMn, ACCo and ACNi are 11.06, 16.32 and 21.30 J/cm². The ACMn shows lower limiting threshold than ACCo and ACNi. The obtained third-order NLO response and better optical limiting threshold value suggests that the compounds can be used as a promising material for developing photonic devices, optical switches and optical power limiting applications.

Conclusions

Three new salen-type complexes containing azobenzene (ACMn, ACCo, ACNi) moieties have been synthesized and characterized. Each complex showed absorption peak of 400 nm in UV-Vis and CD measurements, with ACNi giving the largest absorption wavelength and ACMn giving the strongest absorption intensity. These complexes by introducing azo-moiety as well as beneficial charge transfer to anchoring -COO⁻ groups, absorption bands shifted to around 400 nm and enhanced their intensity. Also, electrochemical data suggested that it is possible to inject electron to TiO₂ and regenerate dye.

Among the synthesized complexes, the Mn complex has the biggest oxidation-reduction potential difference and ACMn

showing a band at 377 nm, is considered as the most beneficial as DSSC dye neglecting the loss of the present cell.

The Z-scan result of the complexes confirms the reverse saturable absorption behaviour. The obtained high value of third-order susceptibility suggests the complexes can be used for nonlinear optical applications. The obtained lower optical limiting threshold values is better for optical limiting materials.

Supporting Information

Morecular structure and PDOS with orbital contribution of each complexes. Also, UV-Vis spectra from DFT calculation.

References

1. B. O'Regan and M. Grätzel, *Nature*, 1991, **353**, 737.
2. T. Kinoshita, D. Y. Joanne, S. Uchida, T. Kubo and H. Segawa, *Nature Photonics*, 2013, **7**, 535.
3. T. Jella, M. Srikanth, R. Bolligara, Y. Soujanya, S. P. Singh and L. Giribabu, *Dalton Trans.*, 2015, **44**, 14697.
4. N. Chadwick, D. K. Kumar, A. Ivaturi, B. A. Grew, H. M. Upadhyaya, L. J. Yellowless and N. Robertson, *Eur. J. Inorg. Chem.*, 2015, **29**, 4878.
5. S. Mukherjee, D. N. Bowman and E. Jakubikova, *Inorg. Chem.*, 2015, **54**, 560.
6. T. C. B. Harlang, L. Yizhu, O. Gordivska and L. A. Fredin, *Nature Chem.*, 2015, **7**, 883.
7. M. W. Mara, D. N. Bowman, O. Buyukcakir, M. L. Shelby, K. Haldrup, L. Huang, M. R. Harpham, A. B. Stickrath, X. Zhang, J. F. Stoddart, A. Coskun, E. Jakubikova and L. X. Chen, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 2015, **137**, 9670.
8. Y. Jia, F. Gou, R. Fang, H. Jing and Z. Zhu, *Chin. J. Chem.*, 2014, **32**, 513.
9. E. Ouskova, J. Vapaavuori and M. Kaivola, *Optical Materials Express*, 2011, **1**, 1463.
10. S. Kubo, R. Taguchi, S. Hadano, M. Narita, O. Watanabe, T. Iyoda and M. Nakagawa, *ACS Appl. Mater. Interface*, 2014, **6**, 811.
11. A. Yamazaki and T. Akitsu, *RSC Adv.*, 2012, **2**, 2975.

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12. R. Shoji, S. Ikenomoto, N. Sunaga, M. Sugiyama and T. Akitsu, *J. Appl. Sol. Chem. Model*, 2016, **5**, 48.
13. M. Yamaguchi, S. Noor and T. Akitsu, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 2017, **94**, 761.
14. K. Takahashi, S. Tanaka, M. Yamaguchi, Y. Tsunoda, T. Akitsu, M. Sugiyama, R. K. Soni and D. Moon, *Journal of the Korean Chemical Society*, 2017, **61**, 129.
15. S. Yamane, Y. Hiyoshi, S. Tanaka, S. Ikenomoto, T. Numata, K. Takakura, T. Haraguchi, M. A. Palafox, M. Hara, M. Sugiyama and T. Akitsu, *J. Chem. Chem. Eng.*, 2018, **11**, 135.
16. T. Numata, S. Ikenomoto and T. Akitsu, *IUCrData*, 2013, **1**, x160252.
17. C. P. Pandhurnekar, E. M. Meshram, H. N. Chopde and R. Batra, *J. Org. Chem. Int.*, 2013, 582079.
18. M. J. Frisch, G. W. Trucks, H. B. Schlegel, G. E. Scuseria, M. A. Robb, J. R. Cheeseman, G. Scalmani and V. Barone, *et al.*, 2009. Gaussian 09, Revision D.01, Gaussian, Inc., Wallingford CT, 2009.
19. Z.-Z. Lu, J.-D. Peng, A.-K. Wu, C.-H. Lin, C.-G. Wu, K.-C. Ho, Y.-C. Lin and K.-L. Lu, *Eur. J. Inorg. Chem.*, 2016, **8**, 1214.
20. G. D.Sharma, S. P. Singh, R. Kurchania and R. J. Ball, *RSC Adv.*, 2013, **3**, 6036.
21. M. Sheik-bahae, A. A. Said and E. W. Van stryland, *Optics Letters*, 1989, **14**, 95.
22. M. Sheik-Bahae, A. A. Said, T. Wei, D. J. Hagan and E. W. Van Stryland, *IEEE Journal of Quantum Electronics*, 1990, **26**, 760.
23. Q. Gong, Y. Sun, Z. Xia, Y. H. Zou, Z. N. Gu, X. H. Zhou and D. Qiang, *Journal of Applied Physics*, 1992, **71**, 3025.
24. K. N. Sharafudeen, A. Adithya, S. Vijayakumar, P. Sudheesh, B. Kalluraya and K. Chandrasekharan, *Current Applied Physics*, 2011, **11**, 1089.
25. M. C. Sreenath, I. Hubert Joe and V. K. Rastogi, *Dyes and Pigments*, 2018, **157**, 163.

